

cide was not available, some farmers spot-sprayed with kerosene, petroleum, and diesel oils. Kerosene sprays were reported to have performed better than pesticides. We compared the efficacy of insecticide dusts and kerosene in laboratory tests (Table 2).

One-gram insecticide dust formulation was spread evenly in a 21-cm petri dish and final-instar larvae were released. One millimeter of kerosene was placed in a petri dish of the same size. A 1:4:40 mixture of kerosene, common salt, and water caused larval mortality equal to that with quinalphos (5%) and methyl-parathion (2%) dusts. □

Table 2. Comparative efficacy of kerosene and insecticide dusts against rice ear-cutting caterpillar.

Treatment ^a	Mortality ^b of last-instar larvae at indicated time after treatment (%)		
	15 min	30 min	60 min
BHC 10D	17 c	80 b	97 ab
Carbaryl 5D	20 c	27 c	73 c
Malathion 5D	23 c	77 b	100 a
Quinalphos 5D	77 a	100 a	100 a
Methyl parathion 2D	80 a	100 a	100 a
Kerosene + common salt + water (1:4:40)	83 a	100 a	100 a
Kerosene + water (1:4)	63 b	83 b	90 bc
Common salt + water (1:4)	0 d	3 d	10 d
Water	0 d	0 d	0 d

^aD = percent dust formulation. ^bIn a column, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

Insecticide resistance in brown planthoppers of Malaysia

K. L. Heong, Crop Protection, Malaysian Agricultural Research and Development Institute, Serdang, Malaysia

Recent toxicological studies on insecticidal effects of some carbamates commonly used to control brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* in Malaysia suggest that insecticide resistance may be developing.

In 1982 BPH were collected from fields of MR1, a local susceptible variety, in Tanjung Karang. They were cultured in the greenhouse on MR1 for 10 to 15 generations. One-day-old BPH adult females

from this culture were treated, using a microapplicator, with various concentrations of MTMC diluted with acetone. Before treatment, the insects were anesthetized with CO₂. Treated insects were allowed to recover in a petri dish before being released onto 2-week-old MR1 rice plants in mylar film cages. Mortality was recorded after 24h.

Toxicological studies in 1977 used BPH collected from fields of Mat Chandu, a local susceptible variety in Bumbong Lima. BPH were reared on TN1 in the greenhouse for 20-25 generations before the studies were carried out. The same test procedure was used, except that the treated hoppers were released onto

2-week-old TN1 rice plants.

Data from both studies were analyzed by a probit analysis computer program from Imperial College, Silwood Park, which performs independent single analysis and joint analysis with parallel data. If the data do not contradict the hypothesis of parallelism, the program compares effectiveness in terms of relative potencies.

Data show that BPH populations in Malaysia have become more resistant to MTMC between 1977 and 1982. During those years, a relative potency increase of 19.42 has developed, perhaps caused by the increased use of MTMC dust for BPH control. □

Cytogenetic variations between *Nilaparvata bakeri* (Muir) and *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) planthoppers

R. C. Saxena, associate entomologist, IIRRI, and principal research scientist, International Centre of Insect Physiology and Ecology, P. O. Box 30772, Nairobi, Kenya; and A. A. Barrion, research fellow, IIRRI

Populations of planthopper species *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens* recently were found coexisting on a weed grass *Leersia hexandra* (L.) Swartz, which grows abundantly in ditches along rice fields at the IIRRI experimental farm, Los Baños. The planthoppers can be distinguished by genitalia. The grass-infesting *N. lugens* is a distinct deviant of the rice-infesting *N. lugens* brown planthopper and is sus-

pected to be another biotype.

Hybridization studies were conducted to determine the genetic proximity between *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens*. Genetic crosses showed minimal compatibility and proved that natural hybridization is impossible. Cytogenetic investi-

gations were made to elucidate specific relationships and observed phenotypic segregations of progenies in reciprocal heterogamic crosses.

Using the technique for preparation of brown planthopper chromosomes, actively dividing testicular cells of newly

Variations in diploid chromosomal complement and sex-determining mechanisms of *N. bakeri* and *N. lugens*.

Species	Chromosome number (2n)	Variations		
		Sex-determining mechanism		Complete genome and prospective gametes
<i>N. bakeri</i>	Female: 30	XX	14 II + XX	→ 14 I + X ova
	Male: 29	XO	14 II + XO	→ 14 I + X sperms → 14 I + O sperms
<i>N. lugens</i>	Female: 30	XX	14 II + XX	→ 14 I + X ova
	Male: 30	XY	14 II + XY	→ 14 I + X sperms → 14 I + Y sperms